

Supporting Information

Suid DNA and contamination

It is known that lab reagents are often contaminated by DNA from various species including pig (*Sus scrofa*) (Leonard et al. 2007). We identified porcine viruses, such as porcine circovirus, porcine parvovirus and torque teno sus virus in our samples. The fact that we did not find these sequences in the negative controls argues against general pig DNA contamination. Moreover, *Sus barbatus*, an endemic pig species found in the region where leeches were sampled, was identified by metabarcoding (Axtner et al. 2019) as leech host in 3 (L7, L8, L37) out of the 5 samples positive to porcine viruses. Furthermore, in order to understand if there was pig DNA contamination in our data, we mapped the reads from the samples which were positive for porcine viruses to the mitochondrial genomes of both *Sus scrofa* and *Sus barbatus*, since often mitochondrial genomes are obtained from capture experiments as byproducts, and we observed that the mitochondrial reads had higher identity to the *Sus barbatus* mitochondrial genome than to *Sus scrofa*. Finally, pig viruses were not identified in the water samples. This suggests that the porcine viruses found in the leech samples did not derive from pig, *Sus scrofa*, DNA contamination, but rather from bearded pigs the leech had fed on.

Supplementary Figure Legends

Suppl. Fig. 1. Evolutionary relationships of the partial *L* gene sequence of the rhabdoviruses identified in the leech bloodmeals (in red) with representatives of the *Rhabdoviridae* family. The consensus sequences of the contigs found in leech samples were used as representative sequence. The main genera of the *Rhabdoviridae* family are indicated on the right. The tree was inferred using the maximum-likelihood method with the GTR+G+I model and node robustness assessed with 500 rapid bootstrap pseudoreplicates. The tree is scaled according to the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. The tree is rooted arbitrarily on one of two basal clades (genera *Almendravirus* and *Bahivavirus*) that comprise viruses isolated from mosquitoes. Abbreviations and accession numbers of reference sequences are reported in <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1004664.s013> (Walker et al. 2015).

Suppl. Fig. 2. Genomic regions covered by the *Vesiculovirus* (A), *Ephemerovirus* (B) and *Lyssavirus* (C) contigs (black bars) identified in leech bloodmeals and corresponding RNA oligonucleotides bait (blue bars) positions. The sequences of the PCR primers and PCR products used to confirm the *Lyssavirus* contigs are shown in panel D.

Suppl. Fig. 3. Evolutionary relationships of the partial *RNA-dependent RNA polymerase* gene (orf1ab) sequence of the coronavirus identified in the leech bloodmeals (in red) with representatives of the *Coronaviridae* family. The consensus of the 16 contigs found in leech samples was used as representative sequence. The four genera (*Alpha-*, *Beta-*, *Gamma-* and *Delta-coronavirus*) of the *Coronaviridae* family are indicated. The betacoronaviruses are further divided into four (a-d) subgroup clusters. The tree was inferred using the maximum-likelihood method with the GTR+G+I model and node robustness assessed with 500 rapid bootstrap pseudoreplicates. The tree is scaled according to the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. The tree is midpoint-rooted for purposes of clarity. CoV: coronavirus.

Suppl. Fig. 4. Genomic region covered by the *Coronaviridae* contigs (black bars) identified in leech bloodmeals and corresponding RNA oligonucleotides bait (blue bars) positions.

Suppl. Fig. 5. Genomic regions covered by contigs (black bars) of the three *Anelloviridae* – Torque teno sus virus (A), giant panda anellovirus (C) and *Paguma larvata* torque teno virus (E) – identified in leech bloodmeals and corresponding RNA oligonucleotides bait (blue bars) positions. The sequences of the PCR primers and PCR products used to confirm the Torque teno sus virus, giant panda anellovirus and *Paguma larvata* torque teno virus contigs are shown in panels B, D and F, respectively. Accession numbers of the sequences generated in this study: MT444470 (L08); MT444471 (L37); MT444466 (L17); MT444467 (L36); MT444468 (L07); MT444469 (L39); MT444458-63 (L39_1-6); MT444464 (L21); MT444465 (L25).

Suppl. Fig. 6. Genomic regions covered by the porcine circovirus (A) and porcine parvovirus (C) contigs (black bars) identified in leech bloodmeals and corresponding RNA oligonucleotides bait (blue bars) positions. The sequences of the PCR primers and PCR products used to confirm the porcine circovirus contigs are shown in panel B. Accession numbers of the sequences generated in this study: MT444451 (L14_1); MT444453 (L14_2); MT444452 (L8). The porcine circovirus sequences were not submitted to Genbank because identical to the reference.

Suppl. Fig. 7. Evolutionary relationships of the partial *replicase* (*NS1*) gene sequence of the parvovirus identified in the leech bloodmeals (in red) with representatives of the *Parvovirinae* subfamily (*Parvoviridae* family). The main genera (*Ave-*, *Copi-*, *Dependo-*, *Erythro-*, *Proto-*, and *Tetra-parvovirus*) of the *Parvovirinae* subfamily are indicated on the right. The tree was inferred using the maximum-likelihood method with the GTR+G+I model and node robustness assessed with 500 rapid bootstrap pseudoreplicates. The tree is scaled according to the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. The tree is midpoint-rooted for purposes of clarity. PV: parvovirus; AAV: adeno-associated virus.

Suppl. Fig. 8. Genomic regions covered by the Equid herpesvirus (EHV) contigs (red bars) identified in the water samples and corresponding RNA oligonucleotides bait (blue bars) positions. An enlargement of the three different regions covered is shown in panels B, C and D. The sequence of the product of the nested panherpes PCR targeting the *DNA polymerase* gene which was used to confirm the presence of EHV in the samples is shown in panels A and E (enlargement) in green. Accession numbers of the sequences generated in this study: MT444456 (WM3-membrane glycoprotein G); MT444457 (WM3-DNA packaging protein). The WM20 equid herpesvirus 1 sequence was not submitted to Genbank because identical to the reference.

Suppl. Fig. 9. Genomic regions covered by the *Retroviridae* (A), *Adenoviridae* (B) and *Papillomaviridae* (C) contigs (black bars) identified in sediment samples and corresponding RNA oligonucleotides bait (blue bars) positions. The sequence of the product of the PCR targeting the *env* gene which was used to confirm the presence of JSRV in sample SM3 is shown in light green (A). Accession numbers of the sequences generated in this study: MT444454 (ST38 papillomavirus); MT444455 (SM20 adenovirus); MT4444845 (SM6-enJSRV-5); MT444485 (enJSRV-13); MT444486 (SM6-Enzootic tumour virus CQ1); MT444487 (SM6-Enzootic tumour virus Shaanxi4).

Suppl. Fig. 10. Evolutionary relationships of the partial *E1-E2* gene sequence of the papillomavirus identified in a sediment sample (in red) with representatives of the *Papillomaviridae* family. The main genera of the *Papillomaviridae* family are indicated on the right. The tree was inferred using the maximum-likelihood method with the GTR+G+I model and node robustness assessed with 500

rapid bootstrap pseudoreplicates. The tree is scaled according to the number of nucleotide substitutions per site. The tree is midpoint-rooted for purposes of clarity. PV: papillomavirus.

Supplementary References

Axtner, J., Crampton-Platt, A., Hörig, L. A., Mohamed, A., Xu, C. C., Yu, D. W., & Wilting, A. (2019). 'An efficient and robust laboratory workflow and tetrapod database for larger scale environmental DNA studies', *GigaScience*, 56/7: 1637–48.

Leonard, J. A., Shanks, O., Hofreiter, M., Kreuz, E., Hodges, L., Ream, W., Wayne, R. K., et al. (2007). 'Animal DNA in PCR reagents plagues ancient DNA research', *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 34/9: 1361–6. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2006.10.023>

S1. Walker, P.J., Firth, C., Widen, S.G., Blasdel, K.R., Guzman, H., et al. (2015). 'Evolution of Genome Size and Complexity in the Rhabdoviridae', *PLOS Pathogens*, 11(2): e1004664.

Supplementary Table Legends

Suppl. Tab. 1. Read counts for leech and waterhole samples.

Suppl. Tab. 2. Primers used and amplification results obtained for the leech viral contigs confirmation PCRs.

Suppl. Tab. 3. Leech and vertebrate species genomes used in BLAST searches to identify potential endogenous viral elements among the viral sequences generated in this study.

Suppl. Tab. 4. Best BLAST hit for each viral contig identified in leech and waterhole samples.

Suppl. Tab. 5. Viral enrichment achieved by capture for each sample.

Suppl. Fig. 1

Suppl. Fig. 2

A

B

C

D

Suppl. Fig. 3

Suppl. Fig. 4

Suppl. Fig. 5

A

B

C

D

E

F

Suppl. Fig. 6

A

B

C

Suppl. Fig. 7

Suppl. Fig. 8

A

B

C

D

E

Suppl. Fig. 9

A

B

C

Suppl. Fig. 10

